

TEACHING ENGLISH GRAMMAR AS A SECOND LANGUAGE USING CORPUS-BASED EXAMPLES FOR INTERMEDIATE ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNERS

Alokhon Khaitova

Head teacher of English of Andijan Machine-building
Institute Academic Lyceum
g.otaxonova11@gmail.com
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16353080>

Abstract. The article covers various information about the necessity of teaching intermediate level students corpus-based examples as well as the ways of how to teach them using COCA. Apart from that, the efficiency of corpus-based examples will be given throughout the article.

Key words: language skills, corpus-based pedagogy, corpora, COCA, language atmosphere, higher outcomes, grammar of the register, ELLs, L1.

Introduction. Teaching grammar to intermediate level students is considered to be one of the most vital aspects of language skills to be improved. Normally, intermediate learners have the conception on basic rules of parts of speech, articles, prepositions, the main idea of smaller passages. Besides, they are able to comprehend the instructions given due to their level of language proficiency. To achieve success in terms of levelling up and achieving higher outcomes they need grammar rules. Obviously, not similar to children, adults have grammatical conception of using functions correctly, what is appropriate and what is not appropriate (Moskowitz, 1978, p. 92). Apart from that, Folse (2009) noted that grammar plays basic role in learning the language (p. 1).

Discussion. A number of teachers of English use various methods in order to teach grammar. Green (2018) pointed out that corpus-based pedagogy maintains the learners' awareness on differentiating the language structure in the context. Teachers who are using corpus approach and implementing it into language atmosphere must have the conception of effectively using the corpora (Green, 2018). Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA) is regarded as free online corpora including language samples used to develop classroom lessons.

I have chosen the topic **Indefinite pronouns** in order to present corpus-based examples while teaching. Mostly Intermediate learners partially know about indefinite pronouns, particularly **some, any, no** and their compounds. Morley (2000) defined indefinite pronouns as "an entity whose identity is not specific". However, Folse (2009) noted that ELLs have some confusion on using indefinite pronouns (p. 53). Among those pronouns the most commonly used one is

some and its compounds. The graphs and screenshots below depict a number of examples with **some** and its compounds in the context. With the help of the examples a learner will have understanding on how to use this type of pronoun owing to his or her level. To focus on intermediate level students' grammatical awareness of indefinite pronouns, the Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA) can be used. Once I have registered COCA, I logged in with my e-mail address as well as password. Following this, I wrote the word "**SOME**" with capital letters.

When I clicked on "**Find matching strings**" the frequency of the word appeared displaying 1685783.

The screenshot shows the 'English-Corpora: COCA' website interface. The 'CONTEXT' tab is selected, displaying search results for the word 'SOME'. The results table shows a frequency of 1685783. The interface includes navigation tabs for SEARCH, FREQUENCY, CONTEXT, and ACCOUNT, along with various utility buttons like HELP, TRANSLATE, and ENTIRE PAGE.

In order to collect the data about in which sphere this pronoun is used more frequently, I clicked on the button “**Chart**” and it showed that **SPOKEN ENGLISH** is dominant with the usage of this pronoun.

The screenshot shows the 'English-Corpora: COCA' website interface with the 'CHART' tab selected. It displays a detailed table of usage data for the word 'SOME' across various sections and time periods. A bar chart below the table visualizes the frequency of usage in each section.

SECTION	ALL	BLOG	WEB	TV/M	SPOK	FIC	MAG	NEWS	ACAD	1990-94	1995-99	2000-04	2005-09	2010-14	2015-19
FREQ	1685792	248127	224888	221363	281030	169738	195661	190143	154842	208618	210765	207816	204077	195529	185972
WORDS (M)	993	128.6	124.3	128.1	126.1	118.3	126.1	121.7	119.8	121.1	125.2	124.6	123.1	123.3	122.8
PER MIL	1,697.64	1,929.25	1,809.91	1,728.39	2,228.00	1,434.54	1,551.74	1,561.85	1,292.61	1,722.59	1,683.29	1,667.54	1,658.47	1,585.18	1,515.02

With the help of “**WORD**” search we can get very detailed information about the pronoun “**SOME**”. As above-mentioned this pronoun is mostly used in spoken English whereas academic field shows its rather less usage. Being aware of the frequency of this pronoun in spoken context, students will have the confidence in using it in spoken English.

ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE

International scientific-online conference

English-Corpora: COCA

SEARCH WORD CONTEXT ACCOUNT

See in iWeb Collocates Clusters Topics Texts KWIC HELP

SOME (DET) #67

See also: BLOG WEB TV/M SPOK FIC MAG NEWS ACAD

1. a certain proportion of, at least one. ; An unspecified quantity or number of. ; An unspecified amount of (something uncountable).
D M O C G E

TOPICS (more)

COLLOCATES (more)

NOUN [kind](#), [sort](#), [extent](#), [us](#), [america](#), [washington](#), [john](#), [clinton](#)

VERB

ADJ [obscure](#), [much-needed](#), [unspecified](#), [enterprising](#)

ADV [eg](#)

RELATED WORDS

[something](#), [someone](#), [sometimes](#), [awesome](#), [somewhere](#), [somewhat](#), [somehow](#), [somebody](#), [sometime](#), [handsome](#), [someday](#), [troublesome](#), [wholesome](#), [somewhat](#), [sometime](#), [someplace](#), [fearsome](#), [worrisome](#), [burdensome](#), [bothersome](#), [tiresome](#), [something](#), [foursome](#), [threesome](#), [lonesome](#), [somebody](#), [loathsome](#), [irksome](#), [twosome](#), [quarrelsome](#), [fulsome](#), [adventuresome](#), [wearisome](#), [meddlesome](#), [toothsome](#), [toilsome](#), [venturesome](#), [frolicsome](#)

SYNONYMS (▶ CONCEPT) NEW: DEFIN +SPEC +GENL

CLUSTERS (more)

English-Corpora: COCA

SEARCH WORD CONTEXT ACCOUNT

CLUSTERS (more)

SOME •	some of • some people • some kind • some time • some other • some sort • some point • some more
• SOME	in some • for some • and some • with some • of some • have some • to some • that some
SOME ••	some of the • some kind of • some sort of • some of them • some of these • some of those • some of his • some of my
•• SOME	there are some • to get some • there is some • here are some • to have some • i have some • at least some • there was some
SOME •••	some of the most • some of the best • some of the other • some of the things • some of them are • some of the more • some kind of a • some of the people
••• SOME	as well as some • but there are some • there must be some • that there are some • there may be some • come up with some • there have been some • there will be some

TEXTS / VIRTUAL CORPORA (more)

CONCORDANCE LINES (more)

We can see clusters, related words, concordance lines as well as being distributed into parts of speech with various colours by means of COCA.

Green – adjectives, **blue** – nouns, **yellow** – verbs, **pink** – adverbs. Using either related words or synonyms helps ELLs to be provided with expanded vocabulary and it maintains to deal with the word searching problems while writing and speaking.

ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE

International scientific-online conference

Информационный сайт — Ho x Week 6 - Formative Assessment x English-Corpora: COCA

english-corpora.org/coca/

Личный — Google Д...

Corpus of Contemporary American English

SEARCH WORD CONTEXT ACCOUNT

CONCORDANCE LINES (more)

1	SPOK: 2007: NBC_Today	: But this kiss from the Snickers commercial caused some anxiety [Clip-from-Super-Bo]	Dr-IACOBONI : Big peak of
2	SPOK: 2012: NBC_Today	of this . KOTB: Well ... GIFFORD: So here we have some celebrities that we first found out about , right , in	
3	WEB: 2012: thenextweb.com	kind of bribery ? # The story here is n't that some corporate is trying to buy influence , it's that it	
4	TV: 1998: Millennium	? Oh . No . No , I was just paying some bills how are you making out ? Fine . Except I	
5	FIG: 1999: FantasySciFi	dirt on her . She 's a guttersnipe , comes from some wealthy family but in the sticks . Father dead , stepmother	
6	SPOK: 2019: NPR_FreshAir	that . But you 're only buying yourself time . In some cases you might be buying a few decades . In some	
7	BLOG: 2012: ...discovermagazine...	of the team itself , I mean , surgeon researchers deserve some credit too # Alpha Centauri A is similar to our sun	
8	MAG: 2004: Ebony	her baby wo n't be too fussy about it . On some days Misha rises a little earlier than 6:00 a.m. to sneak	
9	ACAD: 2019: J Intl Soc Prev Comm...	negotiation of the curved root canals has been deciphered . As some degree of canals curvature is present in most of the teeth of	
10	WEB: 2012: ...rs.stackexchange...	and an algorithm give results close to a real problem by some degree that is good enough solution . # Its worth noting the	
11	ACAD: 2013: ExceptionalChildren	to ascertain how many HQ SETs are currently employed or why some discrepancies exist in state-level data reported as mandated	
12	FIG: 2002: Entertainment	n't heard , Snoop (ne Calvin Broadus) has made some entirely lifestyle changes . Yes , the grand pooh-bah of pot	
13	BLOG: 2012: conservativebyte.com	responsibility-you know that . # dee # The new part is some hunk Democrats do not know the difference between a Democrat and	
14	SPOK: 2007: NBC_Today	, that ad 's probably going to work ! Dr-SNYDERMAN : Some part results suggest that this Coke commercial fared well .	
15	MAG: 2015: Smithsonian	FICTION AS IT GETS . BUT SURPRISING PROGRESS IN NEUROSCIENCE HAS SOME ENTREPRENEURS ALSO TO PRESS " SEND " # In London , Benjamin	
16	MAG: 2006: Newsweek	fields to induce changes in brain function , and there is some evidence to may make nerve-cell connections more efficient . It	
17	FIG: 1997: FantasySciFi	He turned to Zayder . " Perhaps we can still recover some evidence of our young man from the belly of the shark .	
18	MAG: 2016: Daily Beast	, " Clinton replies . " We need to drum up some excitement for the campaign , do everything that we possibly can	
19	NEWS: 2009: WashPost	complains that the program is a boondoggle for the landowners , some senior officials are pushing to replicate it at other military	

<https://www.english-corpora.org/help/changeCorpus.asp>

Apart from that, there are a great many examples available with the pronoun "SOME" in the top of the screen in "CONTEXT". For example, "He soon died. I had lost **some** others, but that was a great friendship and I thought about it a lot".

Информационный сайт — Ho x Week 6 - Formative Assessment x English-Corpora: COCA

english-corpora.org/coca/

Личный — Google Д...

Corpus of Contemporary American English

SEARCH FREQUENCY CONTEXT HELP

71	2004	SPOK	CBS_48Hours	in 1999. Two years later, when Generosa was suffering from cancer and needed some extra help with her medications and her children, she asked Kay...
72	2004	MAG	Cosmopolitan	women-to get the stars to fess up, in their own words, to some of their wildest sexapeades. From the actress who got down with a director in
73	2003	NEWS	WashPost	an SPE. Financial Executives International, a group of corporate managers, estimates that some of its member companies have 1,000 such entities tha
74	2003	NEWS	WashPost	It is easier to get an AK-47 than any kind of book or notepad. Some of their village traditions teach them that they can be made immune to bullets and
75	2003	NEWS	Atlanta	this month, the companies agreed to sell three Dreyer's ice cream brands and some Nestle distribution networks to clear the way for FTC approval. #
76	2003	MOV	Down with Love	No, I'm pretty full. Besides, I have to catch up on some reading. Reading? Reading what? Good night, Gwendolyn. What's the
77	2002	NEWS	Denver	was waiting in Wheat Ridge. He soon died. # " I had lost some others, but that was a great friendship and I thought about it a lot
78	2002	MOV	Undercover Brother	. Then I realized... you can't make Oreos. So, I bought some . Some people got jungle fever. She got the flu. - You know
79	2002	MOV	Undercover Brother	I realized... you can't make Oreos. So, I bought some . Some people got jungle fever. She got the flu. - You know. -
80	2002	TV	Dawson's Creek	fun. - Well, We could order some pizzas. - We could rent some movies. - We could play strip poker. - No. It's not
81	2001	TV	Frasier	in the refrigerator. You didn't have to do that. It's not some of those low-cal dinners, is it? FRASIER: Just go look. [LAUGHS]
82	2000	MAG	MotorBoating	has. It's less pure. During a recent trip to Bimini I watched some visitors stop to admire one of the hundreds of photos that cover the walls of
83	1999	SPOK	ABC_Special	of the streets. Every leftist or Islamic guerrilla had a gun, and everybody had some fight that he or she wanted to carry out. So a hotel would get
84	1999	NEWS	NVTimes	in the next year, the world soccer body, FIFA, will pass out some videos of goalkeepers taking one step over the line. Two things are certain:
85	1998	MAG	Shape	- invisible. " Starved for affection, Christine had an affair. For quite some time, the steamy sex made her feel deliciously alive again. But eventually,
86	1997	MAG	Smithsonian	is the place to start looking for ways to decrease our nitrogen use. On some farms, fertilizer is applied long before plants can use it, so that most
87	1996	MAG	GoodHousekeeping	the Underwood Hotel-a dank, sandy space beneath the famous Atlantic City boardwalk, where some of them were forced to live. Antuan kept taking th
88	1995	ACAD	SocialHistory	much indignation over their sluggishness. At times some of the fields were flooded because some of them did not clean out their fallow ditches in tim

ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE

International scientific-online conference

The screenshot shows the English-Corpora COCA website. The browser address bar displays 'english-corpora.org/coca/'. The page title is 'Corpus of Contemporary American English'. There are tabs for 'SEARCH', 'FREQUENCY', 'CONTEXT', and 'CONTEXT+'. Below the tabs, there is a 'Source information' table:

Source	SPOK: CBS_ThisMorning
Date	2012 (120127)
Title	For January 27, 2012, CBS

Below the table is an 'Expanded context' section with a paragraph of text. At the bottom of the page, there is a 'Translate' dropdown menu and an 'Analyze text' button.

<https://www.english-corpora.org/coca/help/download.asp>

In the following table there are some examples which have been taken from COCA:

No	Pronoun	Related words	Example	The source of examples
1	Some	some	<i>I discuss some of them</i>	https://www.english-corpora.org
2	Some	some	<i>Some entrepreneurs are ready to press "SEND"</i>	https://www.english-corpora.org
3	Some	somewhere	<i>Jupiter is somewhere between two and twelve Earth masses</i>	https://www.english-corpora.org
4	Some	somebody	<i>We must fight! Let somebody else fight.</i>	https://www.english-corpora.org
5	Some	somebody	<i>Let me see the purse. Somebody got the jumbo pack.</i>	https://www.english-corpora.org
6	Some	somebody	<i>Somebody is now saying it's not just me.</i>	https://www.english-corpora.org
7	Some	somewhere	<i>Have I seen this shirt</i>	https://www.english-corpora.org

ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE

International scientific-online conference

			<i>somewhere before?</i>	corpora.org
8	Some	somewhere	<i>Knowledge came from somewhere and could influence belief</i>	https://www.english-corpora.org
9	Some	some	<i>Some companies are now offering refunds to customers</i>	https://www.english-corpora.org
10	Some	some	<i>And we need some more explaining</i>	https://www.english-corpora.org

The screenshot shows the English-Corpora COCA website interface. The search results table is as follows:

	SEARCH	WORD	CONTEXT	HISTORY
9	2017 TV Wet Hot American Sum...	some	! " leave behind. Anyway, enough with the feelings. Let's have some fun!? Chums, chums, chums On this we [all] agree? -	
10	2016 FIC Bk:HardAsIce	some	shortly. Can I get you something to drink? " # " Sure, some water would be great. " # " Sparkling or flat? " # "	
11	2015 SPOK PBS_NewsHour	some	we will be right back to the confrontation again. JUDY-WOODRUFF# And we may need some more explaining of all this next week as they continue to v	
12	2014 SPOK ABC: The View	some	advice " Cosmos " host Neil deGrasse Tyson gave a first grader that may have some parents going nuclear. Welcome back. Welcome back. It is Black Fr	
13	2014 NEWS Pittsburgh	some	on a whim, figuring this is as good a day as any to blow some people up, and when he failed, knowing he'd be the laughingstock of	
14	2014 SPOK NBC: Dateline NBC	some	them were that indeed people would not have been surprised if they had acted out some of the threats that they were alleged to have made. (Video o	
15	2013 ACAD PoliticsLifeSciences	some	destroyed after the peaceful revolution in East Germany in 1990.430 BSU employees have been piecing some together from scraps, but much remain	
16	2012 SPOK CBS_ThisMorning	some	having trouble believing online reviews, look at this from The New York Times. Some companies are now offering refunds to customers in exchange fo	
17	2012 MAG NaturalHist	some	" way, but instead as a whole community, like a multicelled organism. Some cells push up, forming tall ridges that rise into the air like skyscrapers;	
18	2012 NEWS Austin	some	strategy PC game, " X-COM " gets rebooted in this alien invasion fantasy from some of the team behind " Civilization." " In addition to turn-based game;	
19	2012 WEB stevehuffphoto.com	some	tome -- I will show more pictures of all that in the next time (some pics are already there). # As for me, although I love my	
20	2012 WEB popsci.com	some	orgasm. A male has his orgasm (as quickly as in 20 seconds in some apes and human teenagers) and walks off to allow the next male his chance	
21	2012 WEB propublica.org	some	required returns have been filed with the Service and rumor has it that they audited some of them. He also filed very detailed reports with the Feds ar	
22	2012 WEB imdb.com	some	to love them thrusts Proximo: for that. Share this quote # Proximo: Some of you are thinking that you won't fight. Others, that you ca	
23	2012 WEB ...hicagocubsonline.com	some	there this year. So it was a good place during the rebuild to stash some vets and whatnot because nobody was really being blocked. Now as some hav	
24	2012 WEB ase.tufts.edu	some	I don't mean to dismiss its various near-synonyms and connected ideas. I discuss some of them (" culturegens ", " brain bugs ", " viruses of	
25	2012 WEB ...arngeieendowment.org	some	Ukraine, Viktor Yanukovich, announced an ambitious and comprehensive economic reform program. While some key measures, such as a new antio	
26	2012 WEB therewillbesweat.com	some	for some day 2 action. Foam rolling, hip openers, group DROMs and some over/unders in the rack to get going. # Back Squat: # 3 x	

<https://www.english-corpora.org/help/changeCorpus.asp>

ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE

International scientific-online conference

Информационный сайт — Ho x Week 6 - Formative Assessment x English-Corpora: COCA x

english-corpora.org/coca/

Личный — Google Д...

Corpus of Contemporary American English

SEARCH	WORD	CONTEXT	HISTORY
1 FIC: 2008: ArkansasRev	the table so hard coffee leapt from his cup .	Somebody lets worry There's a baby inside her. " #	
2 SPOK: 1995: CBS_48Hours	my mama or your mama at home at night worrying about	somebody coming in the house and robbing her and raping her. I	
3 FIC: 2002: MassachRev	he said , like the sea . Like the taste of	somebody crying he said . # Gary 's parents had a station	
4 SPOK: 1998: NBC_Today	think that they certainly -- If anyone knows Rudolph , and	somebody does and knows where he 's at , maybe they 'll tell	
5 SPOK: 2008: NPR_TalkNation	just - just getting to definitions here for a second .	Somebody earl we had earlier call about pond scum , and you	
6 WEB: 2012: pattyebenson.org	in the nature of a personal services agreement # Mimi or	somebody else conformed the heading and recitals -- and added the	
7 MOV: 2003: Luther	Europe to bow the knee . We must fight ! Let	somebody else fight Let somebody else be roasted like a pig !	
8 BLOG: 2012: thefirearmsforum.com	the idea that it does no good to work , because	somebody else is going to get what they work for , that is	
9 MOV: 2003: Particles of Truth	You think you ever know ... what 's going on in	somebody else is head ? I think you feel people . You get	
10 SPOK: 1998: Fox_Hume	one thing . The opponent 's name is never mentioned .	Somebody else is (BEGIN-VIDEO-CLIP -- ANNOUNCER : The	
11 SPOK: 1992: CBS_SunMorn	the actors , the words in the script are not just	somebody else is life . They are often experiences of friends and loved	
12 FIC: 2014: BkNewFrontiersColle...	, that meant my first name must be Charlie . From	somebody else I 'd resent that as racism . But from Sam	
13 FIC: 2000: PartisanRev	Terezin ? Am I ready to live at the suffering of	somebody else instead of someone else , or at somebody else 's	
14 TV: 1991: Cheers	you guys are either going to have to live vicariously through	somebody else is get your own lives . (scoffs) She	
15 FIC: 2008: BkHavemercy	n't so fine and so sweet-curved as I couldn't ve found	somebody else-and better-to tickle that night . But she was married to a	
16 FIC: 1996: ParisRev	my story . Maybe some other spaceman would read it .	somebody from Desi is planet , and maybe Desi 's been talking about	
17 MOV: 1999: Held Up	me see the purse . Let me see the purse .	Somebody got the khaki pack . - Hey , let 's see the	
18 MAG: 2001: Parenting	over clothes . But kids will still Rick on you if	somebody got their khaki from Polo or somewhere and you have on Wal-Mart	
19 NEWS: 2000: Atlanta	into Chicago and somebody handed them credentials . Inside ,	somebody handed them signs and directed them onto the floor . The signs	
20 ACAD: 1994: Raritan	ood news . You do n't have to there is	Somebody here tonight is pay your bill . Yes , there is .	

<https://www.english-corpora.org/help/changeCorpus.asp>

Информационный сайт — Ho x Week 6 - Formative Assessment x English-Corpora: COCA x

english-corpora.org/coca/

Личный — Google Д...

Corpus of Contemporary American English

SEARCH	WORD	CONTEXT	HISTORY
1 SPOK: 2002: CNN_Movers	of violence on the part of the Palestinians . Some groups	somewhere among the Palestinians are going to break that agreement . There	
2 WEB: 2012: lesswrong.com	including our beliefs . Or even suppose that knowledge came from	somewhere and could influence belief but still did not otherwise	
3 BLOG: 2012: ...tyfour.wordpress...	me to pick them up from my bag that I threw	somewhere around here I 'll find it later when I finish this	
4 MAG: 2018: Ars Technica	one the company is contracted to build in Chicago will run	somewhere around \$1 billion , while a smaller complete system could run	
5 MOV: 1992: Meatballs 4	, was it me , or have I seen this shirt	somewhere before the shirt . I see the 10 has taste .	
6 FIC: 2018: Analog	have released a whopping 1012 to 10 " grams of gases .	somewhere between a million and a billion metric tonnes.3 # But that ,	
7 NEWS: 1999: CSMonitor	and a durable cover with tasteful graphics that create an aure	somewhere between high and intellectual . It 's a book that would look	
8 WEB: 2012: vulture.com	hurdle the band 's already cleared . Now it is poised	somewhere between with main acclaim and genuine crossover . " There	
9 BLOG: 2012: amptoons.com	the time to calculate the exact percentage , but it is	somewhere between the two numbers I 've quoted) . # So not	
10 ACAD: 1999: Mercury	The most recent models indicate that the core of Jupiter is	somewhere between two and twelve Earth masses , whereas on theoretical	
11 MAG: 1998: Newsweek	parts of the world . In Thailand and Sri Lanka ;	somewhere between two and five of every 100,000 women die of breast tumors	
12 FIC: 2018: Fan Fic	not . Like someone cares but they don't . Like I belong	somewhere but anywhere but here . Behind my smile is a hurting heart	
13 TV: 2010: Hawthorne	things , it started off shiny and new , and ...	Somewhere down the line ... Lost its luster . Well , I got	
14 MOV: 2004: Metallica: Some Kind...	a title . Nothing . Me and James did not meet	somewhere else and came in here with material , with songs , with	
15 MAG: 2009: Astronomy	hole would not disappear forever . It would simply pop up	somewhere else in the universe . - Elliot Quataert , Theoretical	
16 MAG: 2012: Sunset	this label , each in collaboration with a wordmaking legend from	somewhere else in the world . Flagship Sy rah : Sequel (\$50	
17 BLOG: 2012: frontpagemag.com	that they sign a declaration rejecting Islam or be shunted	somewhere else on the basis that Il Mohammedans are potentially seditious	
18 BLOG: 2012: montevidayo.com	it met the greater subject . # Then what stirred was	somewhere else that kept this a part of it . # We are	
19 MOV: 2004: Metallica: Some Kind...	out enough in Metallica , he needed to get it out	somewhere else And I totally understand that now . And ... On	
20 FIC: 2004: FantasySciFi	I was similar in kind once , but I came from	somewhere else It live on the credulity of others is n't in	

<https://www.english-corpora.org/help/changeCorpus.asp>

SEARCH	WORD	CONTEXT	HISTORY
4 TV: 1998: Millennium	? Oh . No . No . I was just paying	some bills how are you making out? Fine . Except I	
5 FIG: 1999: FantasySciFi	dirt on her . She 's a guttersnipe , comes from	some low-grade family but in the sticks . Father dead , stepmother	
6 SPOK: 2019: NPR_FreshAir	that . But you 're only buying yourself time . In	some cases you might be buying a few decades . In some	
7 BLOG: 2012: ...discovermagazine....	of the team itself , I mean . researchers deserve	some credit too # Alpha Centauri A is similar to our sun	
8 MAG: 2004: Ebony	her baby wo n't be too fussy about it . On	some days Mishu rises a little earlier than 6:00 a.m. to sneak	
9 ACAD: 2019: J Intl Soc Prev Comm...	negotiation of the curved root canals has been deciphered . As	some degree of canal curvature is present in most of the teeth of	
10 WEB: 2012: ...rs.stackexchange....	and an algorithm give results close to a problem by	some degree that good enough solution . # Its worth noting the	
11 ACAD: 2013: ExceptionalChildren	to ascertain how many HQ SETs are currently employed or why	some discrepancies exist in state-level data reported as mandated	
12 FIG: 2002: Entertainment	n't heard , Snoop (ne Calvin Broadus) has made	some brownie lifestyle changes . Yes , the grand pooh-bah of pot	
13 BLOG: 2012: conservativebyte.com	responsibility-you know that . # dee # The part is	some time Democrats do not know the difference between a Democrat and	
14 SPOK: 2007: NBC_Today	, that ad 's probably going to work ; Dr-SNYDERMAN :	Some new results suggest that this Coke commercial fared well .	
15 MAG: 2015: Smithsonian	FICTION AS IT GETS . BUT SURPRISING PROGRESS IN NEUROSCIENCE HAS	SOME ENTREPRENEURS STAY TO PRESS " SEND " # In London , Benjamin	
16 MAG: 2006: Newsweek	fields to induce changes in brain function , and there is	some evidence it may make nerve-cell connections more efficient . It	
17 FIG: 1997: FantasySciFi	He turned to Zayder . " Perhaps we can still recover	some evidence of our young man from the belly of the shark .	
18 MAG: 2016: Daily Beast	, " Clinton replies . " We need to drum up	some excitement for the campaign , do everything that we possibly can	
19 NEWS: 2009: WashPost	complaints that the program is a boondoggle for the landowners ;	some national officials are pushing to replicate it at other military	
20 TV: 1997: Weird Science	here ? Just kissing some brass , baby . Laying down	some new lines on my horn . Carry on . For a high	
21 BLOG: 2012: ...ricanindependent....	now . I buy from the Boy Scouts , though .	Some Girl Scout groups are worse than others , but from what I	
22 BLOG: 2012: designsponge.com	can find a great little Cynthia Vincent smock , pick up	some great stationery and meet the resident yellow lab lger at the	
23 MOV: 2003: Latter Days	as a waiter on wheels Great . I will give you	some new pants and roller skates as a fulfillment of a dream For	

<https://www.english-corpora.org/help/changeCorpus.asp>

Conclusion. Teaching English grammar for those whose L1 is not English has been a challenging practice. Particularly, providing ELLs with learned language patterns while teaching requires to have an understanding of grammar of the register. As it was previously stated, since indefinite pronouns are considered to be confusing, students should be taught discrepancies between the types of pronouns as well as the usage of them by giving them more examples in the context. By emphasizing indefinite pronouns students whose L1 is not English enhance their writing and speaking skills as it is the requirement for obtaining a language proficiency certificate. Thus, with the help of corpus-based examples, specifically, COCA teachers can effectively teach the topic and provide the students with an authentic texts and articles as well. Or more precisely, COCA is advantageous in terms of increasing students' awareness of any kind of language structure as well as comprehending the discrepancies between and observing various situations coming in the context.

References:

1. Folse, K. (2009). Keys to teaching grammar to English language learners: A practical handbook. University of Michigan Press.
2. Green, B. A. (2018). Corpora in Language Learning. In Lontas, (Ed.),
3. The TESOL Encyclopedia of English Language Teaching. Wiley.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118784235.eelt0397>

4. Morley, G. D. (2000). Syntax in functional grammar: An introduction to lexicogrammar in systemic linguistics. A&C Black.
5. Moskowitz, B. A. (1978). The acquisition of language. Scientific American, 239(5), 92-109.
6. <https://www.english-corpora.org>
7. <https://www.english-corpora.org/help/changeCorpus.asp>
8. <https://www.english-corpora.org/coca/help/download.asp>

